

1

Green Synthesis of ZnO NPs using Capping Agent: Ultra-Sonication Treatment

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Abstract:

Nano-sized ZnO metal oxide was prepared by Green Synthesis method using capping agent, further synthesized material was assisted with ultra-sonication treatment. This material has been investigated for their structural properties. X-ray diffraction pattern reveals that pure zinc oxide was synthesized successfully. Also, calculated average particle size found to be 85.46 nm. Also synthesized powder contains Zn and O elements only without any impurity.

Keywords: Nano-size ZnO, Ultra –Sonication, X-ray Diffraction (XRD).

1. Introduction

In new era of materials science and electronic devices semiconductor materials have great potential to enhance electronic devices different passive properties. Green synthesis approach of nano-sized particle is depend up on green chemistry principles which include the structure and morphological of nanoparticles using non-toxic chemicals, reusable material, environmentally friendly solvents and finally product that is synthesized nano material should be degradable waste product. Green synthesis will be done using biological systems like bacteria, fungi, algae, plants, yeasts and actinomycetes [1]. Among these systems; plant extract systems more appropriate method to synthesize Nano-sized metal oxide materials like ZnO and etc. As Green synthesized metal oxides (MO_x) nano-particles like ZnO, SnO₂, WO₃, etc. have high surface area-to-volume ratio, high reactivity, and good size distribution. This type of metal oxides is used in many applications like gas sensor technology, antimicrobial, biomedical, targeted drug delivery, etc. [2-5].

Among the many semiconductor material Zinc Oxide (ZnO) is extensively used material. This material is used because ZnO is a wide-band gap semiconductor of the II-VI semiconductor group of the periodic table and zinc, a transition metal. The native doping of the semiconductor (causes are as yet unknown) is n-type [6-9]. This semiconductor has several favorable properties, including good transparency, high electron mobility, wide band gap, and strong room-temperature luminescence. Those properties are used in emerging applications for transparent electrodes in liquid crystal displays, in energy-saving or heat-protecting windows, and in electronics as thin-film transistors and light-emitting diodes.

To acquire these properties material has unique structure and this unique structure easily achieved using novel synthesis method. ZnO was synthesized by many chemical synthesis methods also ZnO was synthesized using Green synthesis technology [10]. Particles sized of nanosized ZnO material should be controlled by using Ultra- Sonication treatment [11-12].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Collection and Preparation of Neem Leaves Solution

Neem leaves called as *Azadirachta indica* collected from College campus. For cleaning purpose, clean Neem leaves using distilled water after washing kept these leaves in sunlight

for drying purpose further on dried Neem leaves in Oven at 30°C for 24 hr. Furthermore, dried Neem leaves crushed into mortar pestle to get fine power of Neem leaves. Add 2 gram fine powder of Neem leaves into 50 mL of chilled distilled water, stirred it continuously for 5 hr, further the mixture was ultra –sonicated for 10 min to dissolve the Neem leaves fine powder [13]. The obtained solution of Neem leaves was filtered to remove any residue or contaminants. The obtained stock solution stored at 5°C at further experimental use.

2.2 Green Synthesis of Nano-size Zinc Oxide (ZnO) from Neem Leaves Solution

For preparation of ZnO nanosized particles (ZnO NPs), initially zinc nitrate hexahydrate [$\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$] was mixed into Neem leaves (capping agent) solution and sodium hydroxide [NaOH] followed by continuously 3 hr stirring [14]. The white precipitate was centrifuge at 1200 rpm for 10 min and precipitate was settled done at bottom at solution container. Further, precipitate washed with distilled water and ethanol to get fine powder paste. Then, a solid white powder obtained was dried in an oven at 60°C for 5 hr. The product was calcined in a muffle furnace at 450°C for 6 hr. Finally get ZnO NPs powder.

3. Characterization of Nano-sized ZnO

In order to investigate various properties of the synthesized sample, it is necessary to characterize this sample by various characterization techniques like X-ray Diffraction (XRD) Technique. This helps to obtain the information about the different structural properties and particle size of sample.

3.1 X-ray Diffraction (XRD) Technique

In order to get information about crystal structure, crystalline size, purity of sample etc. of synthesized Zinc Oxide, X-ray diffraction was carried out. XRD pattern of the synthesized sample was obtained at room temperature. The scanning angle 2θ was varied from 20-80 degree in step of 0.06° and the step time is fixed at 0.2 sec using Cu-K α radiation.

Figure 1 Shows the XRD pattern of S_0 . The recorded XRD pattern confirmed that synthesized ZnO is highly crystalline in nature. The higher peak intensities of an XRD pattern are due to the better crystallinity.

Using PDXL software which provided with Rigaku Miniflex 600 model, it is confirm that synthesized powder contains Zn and O elements only without any impurity.

Fig. 1: XRD pattern of 0 min ZnO (S_0).

The domain size of the crystal can be estimated from the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the peaks by means of the Scherrer formula [15]. Particle size of the synthesized Zinc Oxide was found to be 85.46 nm.

4. Conclusion

Nano-sized Zinc Oxide (ZnO) was successfully synthesis using Neem leaves called as *Azadirachtaindica* using zinc nitrate hexahydrate as capping agent. From XRD, calculated average particle size found to be 85.46 nm also synthesized powder contains Zn and O elements only without any impurity.

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